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INERRANT

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¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Work package number	WP7 - Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
Work package leader	P11 – EURICE
Abstract:	This deliverable describes the production process, purpose, and target audience of the INERRANT audio-visual materials published in the first 18 months of the project as well as the foreseen and planned audio-visual materials.
Keyword List:	Video, outreach, communication, project presentation

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Executive Summary

This document describes the activities conducted under the INERRANT project to ***produce audio-visual materials as a tool to communicate the project and its advancements to external audiences***. The project activities will be implemented in line with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

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1. Introduction

The audio-visual material is a deliverable under WP7 Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. The overarching objective of this work package is to design and implement a comprehensive dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy that maximizes the project's outcomes and impacts on science, economy, environment, and society in Europe. Deliverable 7.5 pertains to Task 7.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy, Means, and Implementation. The goal of this task is to ensure effective external communication, outreach, and visibility of the INERRANT project – its goals, progress, and results – while maintaining consistency and high quality across all communication materials and channels. Specifically, the audio-visual materials aim to highlight and explain key features of the project. As outlined in the Description of the Action (DoA), these materials include an animated project video that presents the project's main aspects as well as short video interviews.

2. Description of Activities

2.1 Animated Project Video

The 2:20 min animated project video was designed to **bring to life the work of the INERRANT project in an engaging and accessible way**. It showcases INERRANT's contribution to developing the next generation of safer and more sustainable lithium-ion batteries through innovative material combinations and highlights its commitment to a future where mobility is both eco-friendly and secure.

2.1.1 Purpose

This audio-visual material serves the purpose of informing targeted stakeholders and the wider public about the INERRANT project, drawing attention to its aim of safer and more sustainable batteries powering Europe. The goal is to communicate the project's research focus, objectives, and scientific approach in an easy-to-understand manner.

2.1.2 Target Audience

The main target audience includes stakeholders from the battery industry as well as transportation and e-mobility industries. Policymakers and local authorities who can profit from the project's results and policy recommendations are likewise addressed. Furthermore, the video targets the scientific community and professionals interested in research on the next generation of lithium-ion batteries more broadly.

2.1.3 Concept and Production Process

The audio-visual material was produced as a **3D motion graphics animation** to effectively present the project's research context and approach. The visual elements were created and animated by a professional video production company based on a script initially drafted by Pix Videos and subsequently refined by EURICE. With a length of 2:20 minutes, the audio-visual material is short enough to be easily accessible to online audiences while providing sufficient depth to convey the project's main themes.

The purpose and content of the video were first defined by the INERRANT consortium during the progress meeting in April 2025 and later refined by EURICE in collaboration with the INERRANT Communication Committee (CC). It was agreed that the video should briefly present the project’s research topic, approach and goal with a **focus on the aspects safety, sustainability and e-mobility application**.

Subsequently, a detailed script was prepared by EURICE in cooperation with the video production company and the CC (see Annex I). Based on this script, the video producer developed illustrations that visually support and reinforce the narrative. For example, the opening scene depicts a cityscape with cars and buildings powered by batteries, symbolizing Europe’s vision for a greener, safer, and globally competitive energy system. The video further uses animations in front of a grey background that illustrate the internal components of a battery and INERRANT’s innovative approach to material design, helping viewers understand the functioning and potential of lithium-ion batteries; depict the aim of INERRANT to bring its novel technologies to market quickly; and illustrate the holistic approach of the project targeting the entire battery lifecycle. The video concludes with the logos of Battery 2030+ and BEPA in front of a map of Europe, underscoring the alignment and collaborative efforts driving Europe’s sustainable energy future (for visuals, see Annex II). A voice-over in English was added as a narration, complemented by subtitles to enhance accessibility and ensure broad outreach.

2.2 Video Interview Series

The **four-part video interview series** was produced to present the work conducted within INERRANT as well as inform about some key challenges in the field of battery research in an accessible and entertaining format. The video series features interviews with **four representatives of the INERRANT consortium sharing their insights on project challenges and advancements**, and the future of battery research and production.

Interview with Yannick Molmret

Interview with Dorela Hoxha

Interview with Katrien Boonen

Interview with Petr Marecek

2.2.1 Purpose

This video interview series serves the purpose of informing targeted stakeholders and the wider interested public about the INERRANT project and of drawing attention to its core research themes, including **upscaling battery production, safer battery technologies, the environmental impact of batteries, and battery recyclability and sustainability**. The aim is to communicate these complex topics in an easy-to-understand manner while raising awareness and fostering understanding of modern battery technologies.

2.2.2 Target Audience

The main target audience includes stakeholders from the wider public interested in the next generation of lithium-ion batteries research more broadly. In addition, the series addresses the scientific community, stakeholders from the battery, transport, and e-mobility industries, as well as policymakers and local authorities who can benefit from the project's results and policy recommendations.

2.2.3 Concept and Production Process

The video interview series was produced to present the project's research context as well as key topics and challenges. The interviews were recorded by EURICE during the first progress meeting. Interview questions were developed based on the project's work and refined collaboratively with the interviewees to ensure scientific accuracy and relevance.

Initially, EURICE defined the purpose and focus of the interviews, after which the interviewees provided input to refine the questions. It was agreed that each interview would address a specific core aspect of the project: upscaling, safety, recycling, and sustainability. Based on the agreed upon interview questions the videos were recorded and produced by EURICE.

Each video begins by introducing the interviewee with an on-screen overlay, followed by the discussion of the selected topic. The emphasis of the videos is placed on INERRANT's research rather than the individual researchers, ensuring a consistent focus on the project's scientific and technological contributions. English subtitles were added to enhance accessibility and ensure wide dissemination. With a duration of approximately three minutes each, the videos are concise enough for online audiences while providing sufficient depth to present the key challenges of each research area appropriately.

2.3 Further audio-visual materials

In addition to the animated project video and the video interview series, two short videos were produced specifically for social media:

- An interview with the INERRANT coordinator Spyros Yannopoulos reflecting on the first year of the project, its key achievements, and outlook on the next years of the project
- A short impressions video capturing moments and highlights from the first INERRANT progress meeting.

3. Conclusions

The audio-visual materials communicate INERRANT’s activities, goals as well as its expected results and impact to a broader audience. **Target groups** include the following INERRANT stakeholder groups: battery industry, transportation and e-mobility industries, policymakers and local authorities, research and scientific community, and citizens.

The **animated project video** is one important component of the INERRANT communication strategy. It serves as an easy-to-understand presentation of INERRANT’s contribution to developing the next generation of safer and more sustainable lithium-ion batteries through innovative material combinations.

The animated project video goes live on **11 November 2025 at 10.00 (CET)** on

- the INERRANT website <https://inerrant-batteries.eu/>,
- the INERRANT LinkedIn account <https://www.linkedin.com/company/inerrant-batteries/posts/>,
- the EURCIE YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/@eurice_research.

where it is widely accessible to all interested audiences. Moreover, the video will be distributed through the websites and social media channels of partner institutions involved in INERRANT, and shown at scientific (outreach) events, conferences, and meetings, where partners present the work of the project.

The **video interview series** provides an engaging and accessible insight into the project’s work, highlighting its research focus, progress, and the perspectives of consortium experts on the future of safer and more sustainable lithium-ion batteries.

The video interview series was published from **3 July 2025 to 4 September 2025** on

- the INERRANT website: <https://inerrant-batteries.eu/>,
- the INERRANT LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/inerrant-batteries/posts/>,
- and the EURICE YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/@eurice_research.

4. Next Steps

Efforts will be taken to disseminate the animated project video widely by publishing an announcement and promoting it on LinkedIn and the project website. All partners will be provided with a promotion guide (see Annex III) to disseminate the video via their own channels.

Following up on the animated project video published in the first phase of the project, a second video will be produced towards the end of the project. That video, in contrast to the first, will then focus on presenting the project as a whole and promote the uptake of the results of INERRANT.

5. Annexes

Annex I – Script & Action on Screen

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Script and action on screen

Imagine a future where the batteries powering our world aren't just efficient, but also incredibly safe and sustainable. That's the bold vision driving INERRANT, an innovative EU funded project, rethinking lithium-ion battery technologies from square one, starting with the materials.

[1] In an abstract environment ([reference](#)). A battery pops up alongside a miniature city prominently including electric vehicles/cars, both connected by a link. The link begins to glow green, and as the glow reaches the city, it lights up.

INERRANT is adopting a holistic approach to optimize the four key components of a battery cell: anode, cathode, separator, and electrolyte. The team will fabricate safer [anodes](#) for the next generation of lithium-ion cells and develop novel electrolyte formulations dramatically enhancing battery safety and performance. On the cathode side, the focus is on more sustainable fabrication of advanced materials and electrolyte interface optimization to enhance the battery's resistance to physical stress and slow degradation, paving the way for longer-lasting, more dependable power sources.

[2] We focus on a single battery as it becomes transparent ([reference](#)), revealing its internal components: anode, cathode, separator, and electrolyte. The battery then duplicates, creating a split screen with two batteries—one representing a regular battery, the other a new generation of lithium-ion cells. Icons appear for "[Sustainable fabrication](#)" and "[more resistance, longer lasting](#)". The icons disappear.

Safety is a core priority for INERRANT; with new processes being designed to minimize risk while delivering [top tier](#) performance. This [mindset](#) is also [guiding](#) the development of new, scalable standards for modern battery manufacturing.

[3] Still in the split screen, a thermometer appears in the middle showing a rise in temperature in both batteries, a small red glow (signifying heat) appears in both batteries.

Left: The red glow grows in the regular battery until the whole battery is highlighted in red. A caution icon fades in on top of the battery.

Right: In the protected/new battery the red glow is contained and slowly dies down. The new battery gets highlighted in green. A [shield icon](#) fades in on top of the right battery.

Both batteries fade out.

1

Designed for industrial deployment, INERRANT's solutions ensure effortless scalability from pilot lines to full-scale gigafactories. The team is dedicated to quickly building a solid business case, bringing these innovations to market for a swift and tangible impact.

[4] A small building, identifiable as a lab/demonstrator (through text or visual), floats into view. A small battery exits the building. A second slightly larger building floats into view, identifiable as the pilot line (through text or visual). Several batteries exit the building. A third much larger building appears, identifiable as a gigafactory (through text or visual), a large number of batteries exit the building.

But it doesn't stop there; INERRANT is committed to pioneering recycling methods and reducing the use of critical raw materials. The project embraces a comprehensive life cycle assessment, looking at the entire battery journey all the way from environmental footprint to ethical considerations across the value chain.

[5] The facilities fade out. A small battery appears at the center of the screen, four 3d icons pop up in a circular form: raw material extraction, manufacturing, a home with an electric car, end of life. As the battery travels through the circle its energy level is displayed in the middle of the circle: starting at 100% from the first facility, fluctuating when in the home/car then dropping to 0%, and recharging back to 100% when it gets back to the manufacturing facility.

Being part of the Battery 2030+ initiative and BEPA, INERRANT is fully aligned with Europe's vision for a greener, safer, and globally competitive energy system. Through innovation, responsibility, and readiness for scale, INERRANT is shaping the next generation of batteries making them safer, eco-friendly, and truly built for Europe's sustainable tomorrow.

[6] A flat map of Europe appears. The logos of Battery 2030+ and BEPA appear over the map. The text/logos fade out, and small green batteries begin to appear across Europe, and the map gradually shifts to a green hue, while the view zooms out and shows the rest of the world remains grey. The view zooms in on Europe again, and while the map disappears a battery appears with an icon of safety beside it.

Below it appears the project logo, EU logo and disclaimer ("Grant Agreement No. 101147457. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them") as well as the Battery 2030+ logo and acknowledgement: The authors acknowledge funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101147457 (INERRANT) and the involvement in No. 101104022 (Battery 2030+ CSA3).

Annex II – Animated Video Visuals

Figure 1: opening scene

Figure 2: internal components of a battery

Figure 3: depiction of new technology containing thermal runaway

Figure 4: illustration of route to market

Figure 5: battery lifecycle

Figure 6: European collaboration and alignment

Annex III – Promotion Guide

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Promotion of the INERRANT Project Video

As part of the INERRANT communication activities, an **animated project video** has been produced to introduce the project to a wider audience and **shine a light on the key objectives and approach of the project**. The video brings to life the aims of INERRANT in an accessible and entertaining way, while highlighting the project's core topics of **safety, sustainability, market-readiness, and recycling**.

We invite you to promote the project video via any of your communication channels such as:

- ✓ Your institution's or personal [websites](#);
- ✓ Your institution's or your personal **social media and video channels** ([including X, YouTube, Vimeo, Google+, LinkedIn, Facebook etc.](#));

If you wish to directly embed the video on your institutional website; the file is available for download [here](#). Moreover, the video can be accessed via the [INERRANT](#) website. You can also share and embed the [YouTube-Link](#).

[In order to](#) have a strong and consistent communication, we have prepared a suggestion for a **social media post** and a **news release** which you are welcome to use or adapt according to your needs. You can also use the attached visual and screenshots for illustration.

Social Media Post (suggestion)

📢 We're excited to share the new #InerrantBatteries project video with you!

Learn about our work and the holistic approach we employ to develop safer, more sustainable, and recyclable lithium-ion batteries – for a future where mobility is both #eco-friendly and secure.

Watch the clip here: [insert link here]

#batterysafety #batteryresearch #EUFunded

Visuals

News Release (suggestion)

INERRANT Releases Animated Video Highlighting the Project's Aim to Develop Safer, More Sustainable, and Recyclable Li-Ion Batteries

The INERRANT research project has released an engaging animated project video, introducing the project's vision and approach to create a future where batteries are incredibly safe and eco-friendly.

In the video, viewers get insights into the composition of a battery, the novel materials and technologies developed within INERRANT and its holistic approach targeting the entire lifecycle of a battery. The short video uses 3D animations to illustrate INERRANT's aims.

A voiceover takes the viewers on a journey, starting with painting the vision of safe and sustainable batteries powering our world, explaining the design of a battery, its central components and what advancements INERRANT is developing *in order to* make batteries more sustainable, resilient, durable, and safer. Besides INERRANT's innovative material combinations, the video shows how the project is committed to upscaling these technologies to gigafactory levels and pioneering recycling methods.

The result is a video that explains INERRANT's complex research endeavour, while making it accessible to diverse audiences – from battery researchers and industry stakeholders to members of the public with an interest in eco-friendly energy innovation.

"With INERRANT, we are pioneering advancements in materials and processes that promise to redefine what is possible in battery technology, emphasising safety without compromising performance or sustainability," emphasises INERRANT coordinator Spyros Yannopoulos.

The INERRANT project video is now available to watch on [the INERRANT website](#) and on [YouTube](#).

Visuals

